

Supplementary Table 1: List of psychiatric medications in participants treated for anxiety or depression

Meds started by Untreated Baseline Depression	Meds started by Untreated Baseline Anxiety
AMITRIPTYLINE	ALPRAZOLAM
BUPROPION	AMITRIPTYLINE
DULOXETINE	CITALOPRAM
ESCITALOPRAM OXALATE	DULOXETINE
FLUOXETINE	ESCITALOPRAM OXALATE
MIRTAZAPINE	LORAZEPAM
SERTRALINE	MIRTAZAPINE
VENLAFAXINE	PAROXETINE
	SERTRALINE
	VENLAFAXINE